

PROBLEMS OF MODERN LINGUISTICS. THE IMPACT OF NEW WORDS AND PHRASES ENTERING A LANGUAGE

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Annotation. The article provides information about modern issues that are having impact on modern linguistics. Types of problems in language and some possible, wise solutions offered by linguists are discussed in the article. During the article, the effect of modernization to languages is discussed thoroughly.

Key words: technology, language, modernization, environment, language skills, science, phonetics, translation, recognition, upbringing.

Modern linguistics refers to the scientific study of language and its structure. This includes the study of features including grammar, syntax, and phonetics. Modern linguistics regards language as a system. Most importantly, modern linguistics is descriptive, i.e., it doesn't prescribe how one should use language; instead, it describes how natural language functions. Linguists consider that language change as a natural process; in linguistics, a language that doesn't change is a dead language. So a language is always in a changing process, by this it can be improved and new reforms can be added to it. Describing linguistic phenomena is one of the main goals in linguistics. This can include describing individual languages and what is common to all languages or describing how languages differ from each other. When learning a language, simultaneously with the condition of each lexeme, the lexical concept associated with it is formed. If the lexeme is acquired and articulated correctly, this does not yet indicate that the lexical concept has been completed. In the educational process, it should be borne in mind that the

word is simultaneously a sign of reality and a unit of language. Therefore, nonequivalent and background vocabulary needs comment, requires special attention of the teacher. Equivalent vocabulary is the property of culture. If we compare two national cultures, then we can conclude that they never completely coincide. This follows from the fact that each language consists of national and international elements, and for each culture the totality of these elements will be different.

1. Language change: One of the biggest challenges facing modern linguistics is the constant evolution of language. New words and phrases are created every day, and languages can change rapidly over time. This makes it difficult for linguists to keep up with these changes and to accurately describe and analyze language as it is used today.

2. Language variation: Another major issue in modern linguistics is the wide variation in language use across different regions, social groups, and contexts. Linguists must take into account these variations when studying language, which can make it difficult to draw general conclusions about how language works.

3. Language acquisition: Understanding how humans acquire language is another complex problem facing modern linguistics. Researchers are still working to uncover the mechanisms that underlie language learning, including how children acquire their first language and how adults learn second languages.

4. Language technology: As technology continues to advance, linguists are faced with new challenges in developing tools and techniques for analyzing and processing language data. This includes developing algorithms for natural language processing, machine translation, and speech recognition, among other applications.

Language change can also lead to confusion and misunderstandings, particularly when older generations may not be familiar with newer language trends. It can also lead to the loss of certain words or grammatical structures, which can have a negative impact on cultural heritage and identity. Linguists study language variation to better understand how language works, and to identify patterns and

trends in language use. This information can be used to develop more effective language teaching methods, improve communication between different language communities, and preserve endangered languages. One important aspect of language variation is dialects, which refer to regional or social variations in language use. Dialects can reflect cultural identity and heritage, and can also provide insight into the history and development of a language. Language acquisition refers to the process by which individuals learn a language. This process typically begins in early childhood, when children start to acquire their first language(s) through exposure to the language(s) spoken around them. Language acquisition involves a complex interplay between innate abilities and environmental factors. Children are born with certain linguistic abilities, such as the ability to distinguish between different sounds, but they must also learn the specific rules and structures of their language(s) through exposure and practice. Understanding language variation is crucial for developing a deeper understanding of language and its role in society. By studying language variation, linguists can gain insights into how language evolves over time, how it reflects cultural identity, and how it can be used to bridge linguistic and cultural divides. One concern is that reliance on technology may lead to a decrease in human interaction and communication skills. For example, language learning apps may provide a convenient and efficient way to learn a language, but they cannot replace the benefits of face-to-face interaction with native speakers. Another potential disadvantage is that technology may not be accessible to everyone, particularly those in low-income or rural areas with limited access to technology. This could result in unequal access to language learning and analysis tools. There is also the risk that technology may oversimplify or even distort the complexities of language. Translation software, for example, may struggle to accurately convey the nuances and cultural context of certain words or phrases.

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COMPARATIVE LINGUISTIC ANALYSIS OF PHRASES WITH ADJECTIVE COMPONENTS IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK

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Annotation: This article is a section of lexicology dedicated to the field of phraseology, in which phraseology with qualitative components in English and Uzbek linguistics is mainly analyzed from a linguistic and cultural point of view, and the mentality, culture, customs and traditions of a certain nation are studied. Valuable information is given about the phraseological units reflected in it. Studying phrases in both languages, revealing their semantic-grammatical and functional stylistic features determines the relevance of this work.

Key words: phrase, phraseologism, linguocultural, lexeme, morpheme, syntactic connection, phrases with adjective component, comparative phrases, linguocultural.

Linguistics is a general science that arose between the sciences of cultural studies and linguistics, and studies such phenomena as the interaction and